

Developing a Common Schema for De-identification of Personal Health Identifiers in EHRs across Scotland

Arlene Casey¹, Matúš Falis, Franz S. Gruber¹, Matthew Murrell¹, Spyro Nita¹, Amy Tilbrook¹, Charlie Mayor², Katherine O'Sullivan³, Kathy Harrison¹

¹ University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh, Scotland, ² West of Scotland Safe Haven, NHS Glasgow, Scotland, ³ DaSH, University of Aberdeen, Scotland

Introduction

De-identification of health records - the process of removing Personal Health Identifiers (PHIs) e.g. names, dates, age - to enable safe sharing of health data with researchers is an active and important research area [1]. However, the adoption of de-identification tools into organisations delivering health free-text for research still remains low in the UK. Adoption of existing schemas is challenging as health boards process data differently, and PHI entities can differ between nations meaning annotation schemas need to be modified, e.g. the use of Community Health Index number as a patient identifier in Scotland. Generalisability of tools across health record types can also be challenging due to their diversity [2].

Whilst we know privacy risks occur, there is relatively little systematic evidence about their real-world occurrence. Understanding privacy-risk prevalence combined with understanding inter-annotator disagreements helps develop better proportionate risk-based judgements, which minimise risk when approving health data extracts for research. In addition, this helps create an understanding of the most appropriate NLP approaches to support the task of de-identification of PHIs. In this study we worked across the Trusted Research Environments (TREs)¹ in Scotland to agree on a common schema for de-identification of PHIs. We apply this schema to understand how PHI entities occur within health boards and between health board regions, in two different electronic health record (EHR) types.

Methods and Data

Annotation schema development: Following a literature review of existing PHI schemas the four Scottish regional and national TREs took part in a workshop to discuss current approaches to PHI identification and agree on a common annotation schema for labelling PHIs. Annotation was undertaken in brat and eHOST depending on software approvals within the regional TREs. TRE 1 undertook pre-annotation with an existing tool using available structured data, patient first and last names, DOB and CHIs. In addition, the tool used regular expressions to annotate patterns, such as dates, postcodes, hospitals occupations, and medical or machine IDs.

Data: 2000 Discharge Summaries and 2000 X-Ray radiology reports for patients seen in the year 2022. The Discharge Summaries were selected based on the main hospitals within the regional TREs for patients 18+ who were admitted to a ward with at least a 24-hour stay.

Annotator arrangements and Scoring: TRE 1: All files were double annotated for both data sets. Annotation was undertaken by three annotators. TRE 2: All data was double annotated by two groups which consisted of a pool of 10 annotators, 5 assigned to each group, TRE 3: 20% of each data set were double annotated by a pool of four annotators. Scoring was done between pairs of annotators or the pools of annotators. We report F1 scores using strict matching. Note: although there are four regional TREs, one is not included in results reporting.

Results

Among the TREs', Radiology report human agreement of F1 scores are much higher than Discharge Summaries, as there are fewer entities within Radiology reports. Scores were generally higher in TRE 1, which could be attributed to using pre-annotation. TRE 2 had

¹ Organisations who work in partnership with NHS Health Boards to deliver access to health data for researchers

almost 50% fewer names or address-related information compared to TRE 1 and 3. This is a technical artifact of how data are processed, which allows TRE 2 to automatically remove many entities that would normally be placed within headers or footers in these EHRs.

Table 1 Results are F1 % scores listed in order for TRE 1, 2 and 3. Abbreviations: DS- Discharge Summaries, RAD – Radiology reports, GMC- General Medical Council Id, CHI – Community Index Number, UHPI-Unique Hospital Patient Number, – means no entities found,

EHR Type	First Name	Last Name	Title	Initials	Age	Dates	Year	Hospital	Ward	Occupation
DS	95/88/60	95/91/70	99/93/71	72/80/35	94/69/38	97/74/48	95/72/25	95/89/53	83/64/52	79/69/63
RAD	99/96/97	95/95/98	99/98/99	77/87/67	94/77/92	99/81/96	95/80/32	94/71/91	67/ 49/ -	97/68/97
EHR Type	Address Line	Town	Country	PostCode	Phone	Org Name	Build Name	GMC	CHI	UHPI
DS	80/15/13	63/77/66	67/64/80	92/92/71	83/50/53	09/45/63	0/64/17	100/08/0	100/71/68	60/0/0
RAD	0/100/-	100/40/-	67/100/92	-/100/-	100/100/98	67/62/96	-/ -/ -	98/54/99	-/ 98/ -	-/ -/ -

Highlighting Challenges: Patterns of disagreement around entity types and boundaries:

- Double first or last names, marking of dates and years inconsistently, and boundaries on age (often written as 46yo or 46F).
- Local hospitals marked as two entities i.e. town and a hospital (e.g. Fife hospital) particularly in one TRE which supported more rural areas.
- Phone numbers where they included extensions.
- All wards or clinics were annotated as we were interested in how many may be sensitive, for example, those for gender change, HIV, sexual transmitted diseases. Wards and clinics can be hard to recognise when named after clinicians or community places which caused disagreement on entity type or boundaries.
- Occupations mentions, for example, ‘the police found the patient’, disagreement occurred as to whether this occupation mattered in the context of privacy risk.

Conclusion

The outcome of our work was an agreed common de-identification schema which we applied to our data to understand PHI occurrence and how challenging agreement was. Our current work is reviewing the evidence of how and when entities occur to make policy decisions on how PHIs should be treated and consider what types of NLP tooling may work best to identify and protect patient confidentiality.

Study context

This work was supported by The Dunhill Medical Trust [grant number PF2302\2]; Research Data Scotland SDF1; DataLoch (dataloch.org) which is funded by the Data-Driven Innovation programme within the Edinburgh and South East Scotland City Region Deal. Ethical review and approvals for data access were carried out by each TRE according to their Caldicott agreements.

References

1. Kovačević A, Bašaragin B, Milošević N, Nenadić G. De-identification of clinical free text using natural language processing: A systematic review of current approaches, *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*, 2024, 102845.
2. Kraljevic Z, Shek A, Yeung JA, Sheldon EJ, Shuaib H, Al-Agil M, Bai X, Noor K, Shap AD, Dobson R, Teo J. Validating Transformers for Redaction of Text from Electronic Health Records in Real-World Healthcare, *2023 IEEE 11th International Conference on Healthcare Informatics (ICHI)*, Houston, TX, USA, 2023, pp. 544-549, doi: 10.1109/ICHI57859.2023.00098.